

Body Dysmorphic Disorder , Body Dysmorphia

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Abstract

The most important and prominent components of the self are the physical characteristics that are considered the first element to interact with the self and the other within the personal and social interactions that the individual lives throughout the day and in all stages of his life, and highlights the most beautiful in it as a reinforcer of his presence and a major component of his self-confidence and personal abilities. The individual's imposition of himself, his acceptance of it and his affirmation of it begins with his positive view of what he sees in the mirror and what is reinforced through social response, flattery, and positive opinion from others, as well as the low self-confidence and chronic psychological problems of individuals who have been evaluated formally negatively or have been described with qualities Negativity from others at some point in their lives. The ideal body image for both men and women alike haunts the individual throughout his life, and he always strives to reach it until these attempts are about to reach the point of an obsession with care and beauty. The body image an individual perceives determines his feelings of happiness or unhappiness, and affects his mood, social and physical competence (Beck, 2000). Where the World Health Organization announced that (3) million people injured in the Syrian war, of whom (1.5) have a permanent disability, one million children are injured, and (86) thousand have had their organs amputated, of whom approximately (100) thousand cases of various injuries and incendiary and deformed shrapnel of the face and body, including Various operations as a result of amputation of one of the lower and upper limbs, myeloid injuries or cases of complete disability, in addition to many chronic diseases and psychological problems. Those injured received first aid and were transported to hospitals for various medical procedures. They were accompanied by specialized teams, psychological assistants, and volunteers from all psychological and social specialties and the various initiatives that provided various services aimed at providing the necessary psychological service to rehabilitate the injured for life, accept themselves, integrate into society and work to raise their psychological potential and specialized treatment for traumatized war victims.

1. Introduction

What is the effect of body dysmorphic disorder on the level of optimism of a sample of maimed and amputees in the Syrian war? That is divided into the following questions

What is the degree of body dysmorphic disorder of amputated and mutilated Syrian refugees in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan?

What is the level of optimism among the Syrian refugees with amputations or various disabilities and deformities in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan?

What is the relationship of body dysmorphic disorder with the level of optimism of a sample of people injured in the Syrian war?

What is the relationship of the disorder of the body with the level of optimism of a sample of those injured in the Syrian war according to the variable of gender?

Objectives of the study:

The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between the disorder of the body and the level of optimism of a sample of the injured in the Syrian war, and the incidence of disorder among amputees and mutilated as a result of the Syrian events, as the study reveals their level of optimism, and the relationship of body disorder and optimism to the gender variable.

The importance of study:

The importance of the study lies through its theoretical and practical importance:

Theoretical importance:

- It is considered the first of the studies to the best of the researcher's knowledge to link between dysmorphic body image and the optimism variable.

It provides theoretical content about the research variables, which are: body dysmorphic disorder and optimism.

- The study reveals the level of body dysmorphic disorder among a sample of those injured in the Syrian war and refugees in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan.

- It reveals the level of optimism of a sample of those injured in the Syrian war and refugees in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan.

Terms of study:

Body dysmorphic disorder: It is the mental perception or mental images created by the individual and contribute to the formation of the individual's experiences through what he is exposed to in terms of events and situations, so they are subject to modification (Cavafy and Naial, 1996).

Procedurally, it is defined as the score obtained by the subject on the Body Image Disorder Scale.

Optimism: It is the outlook of anticipation in the future that makes the individual expects the best, wait for good to happen, and aspire to success and exclude anything else. Abd al-Khaliq (1996)

It is defined operationally by the degree that the subject gets on the optimism scale.

Amputee:

And procedurally, they are those who have been cut off one of their limbs or part of it as a result of the Syrian events since (2011).

The deformed: the deformed: the deformed is the negative change in the real image as a result of an event that is not in the details and appeared unnatural, and the deformed are the ones affected by some part of their parts by an unacceptable and unnatural change process as a result of injury or exposure to a harmful event, and procedurally they are the injured in the shrapnel and explosions of the Syrian war, which left a mark Abnormal note on their bodies.

The injured in the war: They are the individuals who were injured as a result of the events in the Syrian Republic and were in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan as refugees, and various health services were provided to them.

Limits and limitations of the study:

The results of the current study are limited in light of the following limitations and limitations:

- Human borders: the study sample, which is from the Syrian war casualties, who are reviewing and receiving various health care services in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan.

Temporal limits: where the study was applied during the period from March / 2020 to May 2020.

Limitations of the study: The results of this study are determined by the tools used and their psychometric characteristics represented by the tools that the researchers used in line with the research variables.

Theoretical framework:

Positive feeling, and self-sucking, is the center of a person's outward launch, as he carries all his characteristics to interact with, and with, or through, with the outside world. The self is whatever the individual possesses of the characteristics, qualities and ideas, whether physical, psychological or mental, including the person's values, ideas, wisdom and style, so if the individual is in itself beauty, high morals, and the skills necessary for his life, this will translate into their behavior from the understanding of others, the impediment to their weaknesses and their weaknesses.

As they are not interrupted by the negative thinking practice towards them, that causes emotional problems and affects the daily functions of the individual.

They are their personalities who play with their daily players, and they avoid different social situations, as a means of defending their defects that they believe in the presence of an excessive form. It shows a certain age in adolescence.

Positive body image creates self-satisfaction within the individual, which supports the growth of a mature personality, and negative body image leads to low self-appreciation and is the main cause of the individual's psychological and social problems (Abdullah 2000).

Whereas the concept of the self that circulates on the soul, the understanding of the nature of the human relationship with himself and its effect on their relationship with others includes the concept of the physical self, which includes the physical and functional properties of the body (Al-Dakhil, 2007).

The body image of the slave is important in the formation of the individual's experiences through what he witnesses in their attitudes, so it is subject to change and modification, and it includes the relationship of the individual to his body and how he is perceived, which leads to the main role in shaping his personality and determining his behavior, his thoughts, the image of the body and the change in the personality and the image.

The body image is the mental perception and mental image that the individual creates and contributes to the formation of the individual's experiences through what is presented to them by our events and positions that are subject to modification (Kafafy and Al-Nial, 1996).

It is a complex picture that contains physiological, psychological and social components, and its formation is interfered by emotional and subconscious factors, which Al-Desouki (2006) divides into three components:

Perceived component: a person's accurate knowledge of the size and shape of his body.

Self-component: Satisfaction, Attention, Heart, Body Image.

Behavioral component: the individual's reaction to rest or lack of it towards physical appearance.

When anxiety and appearance becomes a problem, disorder occurs, and many can be cured with appropriate treatment, the important ones are aware that they have a disorder, and they need professional help and not go to aesthetic or surgical clinics.

Previous studies:

(Abu Hammad 2017) The study aimed to uncover the correlation between body image with optimism, pessimism, and feelings of psychological happiness in a sample of adolescents in secondary school, in addition to revealing the differences between adolescents and adolescents in body image, optimism, pessimism, and a sense of psychological happiness. The study sample consisted of 330 male and female students at the secondary level (160 male and 170 female students). To achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher used the body image scale, the pessimistic optimism scale, and the psychological happiness scale on the study sample. The results of the study showed the existence of statistically significant differences between adolescents and adolescents in body image and in favor of adolescents, as well as the existence of statistically significant differences between adolescent girls in the degree of optimism and in favor of adolescents, and the existence of a statistically significant positive relationship between each of the variables (body image, optimism, feeling of psychological happiness.), And it was also found that there is a positive negative relationship between the pessimism variable and each of the variables (body image, pessimism, feelings of psychological happiness).

The study of Al KadyStudy(2009) which aimed to reveal the relationship of future anxiety with body image and self-concept in cases of amputation after the war on Gaza, and the effect of some variables (gender, marital status, presence of children or not, place of amputation, cause of amputation, and duration of injury) and to answer the study questions, the study tools were applied Future Anxiety Scale, Self-Perception Scale, Body Image Scale). From the researcher's preparation, on a random sample of (250) amputations cases, and after statistical treatments, the results revealed: There is a statistically significant relationship between future anxiety and body image and self-concept in amputations after the war on Gaza.

The 1995 study

The study of koizumi(1995) which aimed to identify the level of optimism and its relationship to the feeling of failure among 584 students of the Japanese Fukuya University, and after the application and statistical treatment of the descriptive study tools, the results of the study revealed a negative statistically significant relationship between optimism and a feeling of failure.

Commentary on previous studies:

Based on the aforementioned review of previous studies, there are many Arab and foreign studies that have researched in the field of body image disorder and in the field of optimism, and some studies have combined between the two variables together, as in the Abu Hammad(2017) study, which aims to reveal the correlation between body image with optimism, pessimism, and the feeling of psychological happiness in A sample of adolescent girls and boys, and a study behind 2012, which aimed to identify the level of some variables (life satisfaction, marital satisfaction, psychological compatibility, future anxiety, body image, identification crisis, level of optimism and pessimism) among a sample of amputees in the Gaza Strip who are war wounded, as well as Many studies have dealt with the effect of amputation and various injuries on the individual, such as the Al-Qara 2015 study, which aimed to investigate the relationship between the amputation experience and coping strategies and their relationship to death anxiety among a sample of war victims in the Gaza Strip. And the study behind 2012, which aimed to identify the level of some variables (satisfaction with life, marital satisfaction, compatibility with myself, future anxiety, body image, identification crisis, level of optimism and pessimism) among a sample of amputees in the Gaza Strip who are war wounded, and the judge's study 2009, and aimed to uncover On the relationship of future anxiety to body image and self-concept in cases of amputation after the war on Gaza, and the influence of some variables (gender, marital status, presence of children or not, location of amputation, cause of amputation, and duration of injury).

The Study method:

The nature of the current study required the use of the relational descriptive approach to achieve the objectives of the study and to verify the validity of its hypotheses. It is one of the types of descriptive approaches, which is used in measuring the relationship between two variables, and determines the nature and direction of the relationship, and predicts a certain level of significance in digital form.

The population Study:

The research community represents all the cases present at the Sir Bobby Charlton Center during the research period, which is from March to the end of May 2020, and the number is (247) cases, where the cases are distributed between (91) children and (156) adults, of whom (104) are males. And (52) females were injured in the Syrian events.

The study sample:

The research sample was from all the adult members of the community, whose number is (156), as shown in Table (1).

Table (1)
Frequencies and percentages according to the study variables

	Item	Frequencies	%
Gender	Males	104	66.7
	Females	52	33.3
	Total	156	100.0

Sample selection method:

All members of the community are selected as individuals of the sample, for ease of access for all individuals, for ease of application of scales, and to ensure the highest level of reliability of results.

search tools :

After reviewing the theoretical literature, the study tool was developed, which is a scale of body image disorder, whose final number was (27) statements, and also the Dember et al. (1989) scale was used, Arabization and translation of Dr.

Exploratory application:

The scale was presented by a number of referees, and they were informed of the amendment of the text of the statement or absent from all of it (3) from (10) arbitrators, and then the scale was applied to a sample of (30) students from outside the sample to ensure the validity of the scale.

Body Image Scale:

Scale correction

The scale consists of 27 items, and the answer to a five-point scale represents the following categories in order (always, often, sometimes, rarely, never), which represent numerically 0,3,2,1, 0, respectively, noting that the total score of the scale is (108), and the statistical standard is shown in Table (2)

Table (2)
The statistical criterion for body image scale

73 -108	High
- 7237	Medium
36-0	Low

Search variables: disorder, deformity, body. , Level of optimism. War injured males / females.

The first question: What is the degree of Body dysmorphic disorder of the amputated and mutilated Syrian refugees in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan?

To answer this question, we sought to extract the arithmetic mean and the standard deviation of the degree of the Body dysmorphic disorder from amputated and mutilated Syrian refugees in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, and the table below illustrates this.

Table (6)

The arithmetic mean and the standard deviation, the degree of Body dysmorphic disorder of the amputated and mutilated Syrian refugees in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan.

Field	Mean	S.D	Level
Body Image	79.12	15.942	high

Table (6) shows the incidence of a disorder of disfigurement of the body among the amputated and mutilated Syrian refugees in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, which came with a high grade, with a mean of (79.12) and a standard deviation of (15.942)

The second question: What is the level of optimism among the Syrian refugees, the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, and the different disabilities and disorientation?

In order to answer this question, the arithmetic mean and the standard deviation were extracted from the level of optimism of the amputee victims or the various disabilities and distortions of the Syrian refugees in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, and the table below illustrates this.

Table (7)
The arithmetic mean and the standard deviation ,the level of optimism of the amputated, various disabilities and disfigures of the Syrian refugees in the Kingdom of Jordan, the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan, ranked in descending order

Field	Mean	S.D	Level
optimism	15.90	9.88	Low

Table (7) shows that the level of optimism of the affected Syrian refugees in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan came with a low grade, with an average of (15.90) and a standard deviation of (9,883).

The third question: What is the relationship between turmoil and the distortion of the body to the level of optimism of a sample of those injured in the Syrian war?

In order to answer this question, you sought to find out the whole correlation of Pearson between the upheavals of the body deformation with the level of optimism of a sample of those injured in the Syrian war, and Table (8) illustrates this.

Table (8)
Pearson correlation coefficient of the relationship between disturbance and distortion of the body with the level of optimism of a sample of those injured in the Syrian war

		optimism
Body Image	R	-.702(**)
	Sig	.000
	Number	156

*** Statistical significant at the significance level (0.05). ** Statistical significant at the significance level (0.01).**

Table (8) shows that there is a negative relationship with a statistical significant between the disturbances in the body with the level of optimism of a sample of those injured in the Syrian war.

The fourth question: Does the strength of the relationship differ between the perturbation of the distortion of the body and the level of optimism of a sample of those injured in the Syrian war following the variable of gender?

To answer this question, the correlation was found between the disturbance of the body deformation and the level of optimism of a sample of those injured in the Syrian war according to the gender variable (male and female), as well as the calculation of an average value to show the differences in the strength of the correlational relationship between males and females, as shown in the table below.

Table (9)Correlation coefficients between body distortion disorder and the level of optimism of a sample of people injured in the Syrian war with different gender variants and a difference test between correlation coefficients

		R	Number	sig
Gender	Males	-.728(**)	104	0.402
	Females	-.652(**)	52	

It is evident from Table (9) that there is no statistical difference ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the strength of the correlational relationship due to the effect of gender, where the score reached (0.837), and in statistical terms, it reached (0.402).

Discussion of findings and recommendations:

Discussion of the results of the first question: The text of the question is: What is the extent of the injury to a disorder of disfigurement of the body among the amputated and mutilated Syrian refugees in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan?

The results showed that the degree of injury to a disfigured body disorder among the amputated and mutilated Syrian refugees in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan came with a high grade, with an average of (79.12) and a standard deviation of (15.942). This confirms that the injury, and specifically the amputation of

one of the parties, causes a change in the body image in an unacceptable and unnatural way and impedes normal life and contradicts the aspirations and goals of the individual and makes him feel inferior and unsatisfied and what follows these emotions in terms of psychological and behavioral reactions that appear in the form of disturbance of body image, and the identity of what you have reached His previous studies, such as the Khalaf study (2012) and Al Kady(2009) as well as the Najjar study (1997)), which emphasized the disorder of amputees and those with a disorder of body image and a high statistical significance.

Discussing the results of the second question and the text of the question was: What is the level of optimism of the patients with petroleum-related disabilities and the various disabilities and distortions of the Syrian refugees in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan?

The results showed that the level of optimism among those with amputations or various disabilities and distortions of the Syrian refugees in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan came with a low rating, with a mean average of (15.90) and a standard deviation of (9.883), which confirms the low level of optimism and the level of optimism that forms part of it in the form of troubles in the Hashemite Kingdom. In the options that suit the status of the body, sensitivity to society's outlook, relationships with the opposite gender, friendships, activities, and the inherent feeling of helplessness, which is the result reached by previous studies such as Al-Mashaan (2000), Khalaf (2012), and Abu Hammad (2017), all of which examined the relationship of optimism to mental disorders and disorder The body, and emphasized that psychological disorder increases the level of pessimism and negativity, which also increases the aggravation of disorders and their development, and thus decreases the individual's ability to achieve and anticipate the future and achieve dreams and strive to achieve the lowest level of daily performance.

Discussing the third question and the text of the question was: What is the relationship between turmoil and the distortion of the body to the level of optimism of a sample of those injured in the Syrian war?

The results showed a negative correlation with a statistical function between the disturbance and distortion of the body with the level of optimism of a sample of those injured in the Syrian war. Both genders improve this picture and may develop to very high manifestations of the disorder.

Discussing the fourth question: Does the strength of the relationship differ between the perturbation of the disruption of the body and the level of optimism of a sample of those injured in the Syrian war following the variable gender?

The results showed that there was no difference in the strength of the correlational relationship due to the effect of gender, and this result also confirms that the effect of the disorder on both genders and also that both of them are affected by the level and quality of his thoughts depending on the degree of his affliction with body image disorder.

Recommendations:

After reviewing the research results, the researcher recommends the following:

- The need to include the concepts of positive psychology in psychotherapy, especially with the injured and the missing limbs.

- Focusing on the inclusion of different therapeutic methods for optimism skills that increase the effectiveness of treatment, and work to empower the patient with cognitive skills that raise his motivation and help him set future goals that reduce his psychological disorders and maladjustment and support his psychological construction.

Attention to the psychological aspect and focus on it in the case of any of the physical or organic diseases, and simultaneously with drug treatment or various interventions.

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